

THE IMPORTANCE OF CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN THE COURSE OF ULCERATIVE COLITIS

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Abstract. Nonspecific ulcerative colitis (NUC) is one of the most significant and complex problems in the field of gastroenterology. This is a chronic disease of the colon, characterized by the formation of ulcerative-constructive changes on its mucous membrane. Globally, the number of cases varies from 50 to 230 cases per 110,000 people. Although the disease can occur at any age, men and women aged 18 to 45 are most susceptible to it. Interestingly, smokers have half the risk of developing colitis than non-smokers. The formation of this disease depends on many factors, including infectious, immunological, genetic, as well as external environmental factors. Nonspecific ulcerative colitis is characterized by a long progressive course, seasonal exacerbations and severe complications, which often leads to a high degree of disability. It affects mainly young and able-bodied people. Recently, great importance in the development of NUC has been attached to the state of the immune system, which is key to understanding and predicting the course of the disease.

Keywords: immune system, severity, immunocorrection, lymphocytes.

Аннотация. Неспецифический язвенный колит (НЯК) является одной из наиболее значимых и сложных проблем в области гастроэнтерологии. Это хроническое заболевание толстой кишки, характеризующееся формированием язвенно-констриктивных изменений на ее слизистой оболочке. Во всем мире число случаев заболевания варьируется от 50 до 230 на 110 000 человек. Хотя заболевание может возникнуть в любом возрасте, наиболее подвержены ему

мужчины и женщины в возрасте от 18 до 45 лет. Интересно, что у курильщиков риск развития колита в два раза ниже, чем у некурящих. Формирование этого заболевания зависит от многих факторов, включая инфекционные, иммунологические, генетические, а также факторы внешней среды. Неспецифический язвенный колит характеризуется длительным прогрессирующим течением, сезонными обострениями и тяжелыми осложнениями, что нередко приводит к высокой степени инвалидизации. Заболевание поражает преимущественно молодых и трудоспособных людей. В последнее время большое значение в развитии ЯК придается состоянию иммунной системы, что является ключом к пониманию и прогнозированию течения заболевания.

Ключевые слова: иммунная система, тяжесть, иммунокоррекция, лимфоциты

Relevance. Recent studies confirm the importance of changes in the immune system in nonspecific ulcerative colitis (NUC), which makes it relevant to study the characteristics of these changes depending on the severity and form of the disease. The purpose of this study is to develop clinical and immunological characteristics and principles of immunocorrective therapy for NUC.

Purpose of the study: To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been identified:

1. To identify the features of changes in the cellular and humoral immunity in patients with NUC of varying severity and depending on the form of the disease.
2. To study the state of functional activity of natural killer cells (NKC) in patients with NUC at various degrees of severity and forms of the disease.
3. To study the effectiveness of treatment of ulcerative colitis using immunocorrective agents.

This study has practical significance, as it will allow the development of more effective methods for diagnosing and treating NUC, taking into account differences

in the immune response in patients with different degrees of severity and forms of the disease.

Materials and methods of research. This study included the observation of 96 patients with ulcerative colitis in the acute phase in the gastroenterological department of City Medical Association No. 1 in Samarkand. The average age of the patients was 15-67 years, among whom there were 49 men and 47 women. All patients underwent a standard examination, including biochemical, radiological, endoscopic (sigmoid-fibroscope, colonofibroscope), immunological, bacteriological and histological examination of intravital colon biopsies.

The control group included 25 practically healthy individuals aged 17 to 56 years. As a result of the analysis, 59.4% of patients had a chronic relapsing form of NUC, 36.4% had a chronic continuous form, and only 4.2% had an acute form of the disease. A mild course was typical only for the chronic relapsing form in 20% of patients, moderate in 56.3%, and severe in 22.9%.

The assessment of immune status was carried out in accordance with accepted diagnostic standards. The absolute and relative content of T-lymphocytes, subpopulations of theophylline-resistant and theophylline-sensitive cells, the state of

the B-link of the immune system, the concentration of immunoglobulins of classes A, M, G, the number and functional activity of natural killer cells were determined. The obtained data were processed statistically.

Research results. A study of patients with mild ulcerative colitis showed the following results:

- In the study group of 46 patients, other diseases were detected in 20 (9.2%) of them, such as chronic cholecystitis, 13 (5.98%) patients with chronic pancreatitis, 11 (5.06%) patients with chronic hepatitis and 2 patients with acute appendicitis.

Despite the presence of concomitant diseases, in most patients the symptoms of ulcerative colitis were identified after a thorough questioning and examination.

- All patients had a chronic relapsing form of the disease with a disease duration of 1 to 14 years.

- Analysis of the immune status of this group showed a decrease in the relative number of lymphocytes and a decrease in the relative number of T-lymphocytes, as well as an increase in the relative and absolute number of B-lymphocytes. Indicators of humoral immunity were also changed, with an increase in the concentration of IgE and IgA, as well as an increase in the content of IgM compared to the control group.

- The functional activity of natural killer cells showed only a tendency to decrease.

Thus, in patients with mild ulcerative colitis, changes in the immune system are characterized by a decrease in T-lymphocytes, an increase in B-lymphocytes and immunoglobulins of class A and M. These changes can serve as diagnostic criteria for a chronic relapsing form of NUC with a mild course.

A study of patients with moderate ulcerative colitis revealed the following features:

- In 54 patients among the study patients, a moderate course of NUC was identified, among which 39% had a chronic continuous form of the disease, and 61% had a chronic relapsing form.

- Analysis of the immune system of these patients showed a decrease in the number of T-lymphocytes, T-helpers and T-suppressors. At the same time, an increase was noted in B-lymphocytes. This indicates a deficiency of the T-immune system and an imbalance between T and B cells.

- The level of immunoglobulins IgA and IgM was also increased in these patients, and the IgM content was 2.3 times higher than in the control group. The IgA concentration tended to increase by 1.7 times.

- Patients with moderate NUC showed the lowest levels of T-cell immunity with a predominant decrease in T-suppressors. This immune deficiency is accompanied by a more pronounced clinical picture of the disease.

A study of patients with severe NUC confirmed the following results:

- Severe disease was observed in 22 patients. Against the background of normal indicators of the number of lymphocytes in the peripheral blood, a sharp decrease in T-lymphocytes was detected.

- As in the case of a moderate course, there is a decrease in the number of T-helpers and T-suppressors, accompanied by an increase in the number of B-lymphocytes.

- The level of immunoglobulins IgA and IgM was also increased. IgM levels increased up to 3-7 times compared to the control group.

Thus, patients with nonspecific ulcerative colitis of moderate and severe severity are characterized by a decrease in the T-cell component of immunity, a deficiency of the T-system, as well as an increase in the level of immunoglobulins IgA and IgM. These changes indicate serious disorders of the immune system and may contribute to the development of more pronounced clinical manifestations of the disease.

This study showed that changes in the immune system of patients with ulcerative colitis (NUC) correlate with the severity of the disease and the activity of the pathological process. Even with mild NUC severity, changes in cellular and humoral immunity, as well as low functional activity of natural killer cells (NK)

were detected. With an increase in the severity of the disease and the prevalence of the pathological process in the colon, a deepening deficiency of the T-immune system was observed, which was accompanied by the development of autoimmune reactions and systemic lesions of various organs, including the gastrointestinal tract, liver, heart and blood.

Conclusions:Main conclusions of the study:

1. Disturbances in the immune system (cellular and humoral immunity) in patients with NUC depend on the form of the disease, its severity and the activity of the pathological process.

2. Low functional activity of the NK indicates a severe course and unfavorable prognosis of the disease, and is a criterion for diagnosing its severity.

3. Determination of the state of the immune system (cellular and humoral immunity), as well as the functional activity of NK, can be used to determine the form and severity of NUC.

4. It is recommended to determine the individual sensitivity of T-lymphocytes to immunomodulatory drugs for more differentiated therapy.

Thus, understanding the changes in the immune system in NUC and their relationship with disease severity may be useful for the development of individualized methods for diagnosis and therapy of this condition.

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